

THE ANALYSIS OF HOUSE-LOT CHARACTERISTICS IN HISTORICAL-URBAN PATTERN OF EDİRNE KALEİÇİ REGION ⁽¹⁾

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Abstract

(1) This article is based on Hayriye Oya Saf's 2011 doctoral dissertation titled "A Method for the Analysis of Lot-House Relations in Ottoman Housing Pattern" (Saf, 2011).

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This study, depends on morphological analysis method, claims the necessity of resolving the housing pattern in the historical cities through parameters related to the house and lot. Geographic Information System (GIS) software was processed to visualize the analysis results. Moreover, the study also aims at forming a database, which would help to prepare conservation plans for the urban protected areas, with the new data obtained by using such a resolution. Concisely, it would provide input, for the teams that would create the conservation plans for project; about the features of the lot on which the protected structure is located, how it is positioned within the lot, and how much it fits to the general trend. It is expected that the data obtained from this study would be used as a design guide for the protection and development of historical housing pattern.

Keywords: Edirne-Kaleiçi, Ottoman Housing Pattern, Conservation Plan for Project, Urban Protected Area, Geographical Information System (GIS)

INTRODUCTION AND METHODOLOGY

The majority of the structures protected under today's approach to historical-urban pattern conservation are considered when creating conservation plans and making development decisions. The database for the conservation works is made up of the age, material, structural configuration, plan, and facade features of each structure within the urban pattern. However, new information discovered through morphological study of the pattern can help in the development of more competent master plans. Undoubtedly, the characteristics of streets and garden walls, as well as a building's placement inside the lot to which it belongs, have a considerable role in the formation of the urban pattern. Better-qualified conservation plans could be created if a specific plan type is used on a specific type of lot and how the plan type is adapted to the lot type is understood. This study fits into this strategy by doing an analysis of the urban-historical housing pattern utilizing parameters related to houses and lots, based on the morphological analysis method. It is suggested that the findings can serve as a design manual for the construction of such historical locations. The Edirne Kaleiçi⁽¹⁾ region's urban-historical pattern serves as the case study's main source of information.

(1) *Kaleiçi*, as a Turkish phrase, refers to inner castle area in English.

Table 1. Method of the study

This research is realized in five phases as; literature review and data collection, determination of the parameters, survey, analysis of the study area, and evaluation. The first phase is shaped in the form of two sections. In the first section, the theoretical background, related to the topic, is clarified while the visual materials of Edirne Kaleiçi region, such as plans, sketches, photographs etc., are collected in the second section. The written and visual documents related to the area are also obtained in this section. The variables that could display house and lot specifications in the study area, on the other hand, are

detected in the second phase. The variables are classified under two groups as variables related to the house and lot. The main plan type, sub plan type, location of house, area, and entrance of the house are considered factors linked to the house, while the geometric shape, location, area, plot ratio (PAR), and floor area ratio (FAR) of the lot are considered variables associated to the lot. In the third phase, however, the houses included in the study area selected, existing situation of the study area is drawn on Edirne Kaleiçi map 1/1,000 scale; and the data related to these houses are updated. Moreover, photographs are taken in the area. Besides the literature review, data are obtained by interviewing authorities in Edirne Municipality, Trakya University, and public institutions. The fourth phase is implementation phase. The implementation phase's methodology, which was started by making decisions about the aforementioned factors in the case, is shown in Table 1.

The next step is to arrange the data in the data pool, which is the procedure that follows data acquisition. The creation of building cards and the transfer of data to tables were then completed. On the one hand, it is made sure that the digital maps were set up in a way that would make it possible to transmit the data to the Geographical Information System (GIS) program. Using a geographic information system enables the mapping of variable-based data inventory and analysis findings. This technique would also allow making evaluations through the maps, which would be particularly useful for studies where several houses in a historical pattern would be examined. All data are then compiled in EXCEL and the percentage of distributions in area and mean, the maximum and minimum values for some parameters are obtained. Finally, in the fifth phase, the results are evaluated; and the general characteristics of area are defined.

HISTORICAL AND PHYSICAL STRUCTURE OF EDİRNE

Historical Background and Development of Urban Pattern

Since its location is on the highway connecting to Istanbul, and by extension Europe, to Anatolia, Edirne, one of the three capital cities of the Ottoman Empire along with İstanbul and Bursa, has gained significance throughout history.

Edirne goes back to 35 B.C. in history. There is no concrete historical evidence that pinpoints the precise location of the original Edirne city settlement (Adivar, 1964). Before the Byzantine and Roman eras, Odris is said to have founded the city where the Meriç and Tunca rivers converge (Gökbilgin, 1994). The city was ruled, respectively, by Luwians, Traks, Macedonians, Celts, and Romans in the prehistoric era (Darkot, 1965; Gökbilgin, 1988). When the Roman Empire ruled the city, there were frequent disturbances, therefore Hadrianus, the Roman emperor, built a fortress (117-138 A.D.) for the purpose of defence (Yücel, 2000). There is a way to indicate that the city progressed significantly under dominion of Roman Empire in the 2nd century and first half of 3rd century A.D. The city was given the name Hadrianopolis in honour of the Roman Emperor Hadrianus during this time (Darkot, 1965).

Huns and Goths had been posing a danger to the area since the middle of the 4th century. The Byzantines then occupied the city. The Byzantine era at Edirne lasted almost 1000 years. At various points in history, Goths, Avars, Pechenegs, Crusaders, and Latin Armies assaulted Edirne (Akansel, 1990). In addition to these invasions, the city suffered significant devastation from Avar raids in 582 A.D. and Bulgarian incursions in 914 A.D. and 928 A.D. (Gökbilgin, 1988). The

Byzantine State had been attacked frequently in the sixteenth century. They maintained their hegemony during this time with the help of Aydınoğlu Ömer Bey and Ottoman Orhan Bey (Akansel, 1990).

Beginning in 1346, the Ottomans had a relationship with Edirne. When Sultan Murat (1359-1389) seized the region, the city came into view as a small settlement region surrounded by Meriç River and inside the Byzantine Castle. Lala Şahin Pasha successfully absorbed the city into Turkish rule without resorting to force in 1362. But when the city became the capital in 1365, it cemented its position in Ottoman history (Büyüm, 1982). Following the seizure of Edirne by the Ottomans, settlement was expanded outside the castle (Yücel, 2000). From the moment it came under Ottoman rule until the end of the 17th century, Edirne consistently exhibited development. The city displayed a rich structural pattern with palaces, bridges, caravansaries, inns, imarets, and fountains built in this period.

Up to the 18th century, Edirne was always in the spotlight as a military and governmental base. The city entered a recession in the 18th century, primarily as a result of governmental shortcomings, the 1745 fire, and the 1751 earthquake. The Russian Wars of the 19th century caused a considerable deal of harm to the city; at this time, several areas of the city were destroyed (Akansel, 1990). The lots were organized so that the streets and alleyways were orthogonally crossing in accordance with the new urban design created by the French architects in response to these disasters and wars (Yücel, 2000). The Kaleiçi neighbourhood is located on the westernmost point of the Tunca curve in the modern Edirne city plan, while the Kaleiçi⁽²⁾ neighbourhoods that surround Kaleiçi are located on the eastern portion (Erdoğan, 2006). The Kaleiçi Region, as the study area, is conspicuous for its orderly perpendicular streets that are surrounded by old castle walls, now extinct, located on a slightly sloped land.

(2) *Kaleiçi*, as a Turkish phrase, refers to outer castle area in English.

The Architectural Characteristics of Kaleiçi Houses

The Kaleiçi neighbourhood has a special place in modern-day Edirne due to the number of old houses there and the efforts to preserve them. The houses of non-Muslim residents who left Kaleiçi for political or economic reasons are among the architectural examples to be preserved because of their architectural interest. In this context, earlier judgments and registration decisions were revised in 1985 for the densely populated Kaleiçi Conservation Area in Edirne. This change resulted in the removal from the registry of houses that lacked structural integrity and had no potential for renovation. The implementation of a "Development Plan for the Edirne Urban Conservation Area" followed (Yücel, 2000).

As for the plan characteristics of Kaleiçi Houses, Kaleiçi was a settlement composed totally of wooden carcass houses at the beginning of 19th century. The dwellings that have survived to the present day typically have modest exteriors and plan metric solutions and belonged to non-Muslims. These houses in Kaleiçi, the old district of Edirne, resemble the common plan type with inner sofa. As the primary design element in plan types, sofa is either positioned between the rows of chambers or in the centre of the cluster of chambers. Whether the house has a single or two stories has no bearing on this situation. The lot size, which might be either huge or small, determines which of two plan types is chosen. The draw of these houses is that, as a result of being constructed in 20th century, the two-storey houses' original plan, which featured a courtyard on the ground level and the main floor, has been replaced. Even though the first floor plans no longer serves as the descriptive main floor plan to determine the sort of layout, it nevertheless commands some attention.

Additionally, it has been observed that the settlement's material use patterns have changed as a result of the existence of minorities. Buildings made of brick are replaced with the stone ones. While the cantilever is topped by a hipped roof in vernacular buildings, triangular pediments are common. There are also some peculiar examples, such the sofa being the sole thing on the first floor.

CASE STUDY

Today, Edirne is notable due to its urban layout, historical sites, and old Ottoman houses. Due to its protected urban texture, the Kaleiçi region of Edirne was selected as the case area for the field study. On the southwest side of the city, Kaleiçi is situated in a triangle formed by the Tunca River, Saraçlar Street, and Talatpaşa Boulevard. The Hippodamus urban plan is used for Kaleiçi settlement, the first core of Edirne settlement. The houses (Figures 2 and 3) often feature plan types with inner sofa. On the other hand, there are other housing kinds that have an outer and central sofa. As is well knowledge, the Ottoman housing's lot pattern is referred to as an organic pattern. The study space does, however, have a grid-scheme layout. It is necessary to determine how to arrange the aforementioned plan kinds in a grid-scheme pattern (Figure 1).

In the context of this study, 70 vernacular Ottoman Houses are analysed, and the house and the lot specifications are described. The detected variables for the house within the case study are main plan type, sub plan type, location, floor area, and entrance. For the lot, however, the variables are the geometry, location, area, plot ratio (PAR), and floor area ratio (FAR). Some of these variables were detected during the field study while the others are calculated by using the maps.

Figure 1. Satellite Photo
(This Image provided by the
NIK System, www.nik.com.tr:
WorldView2 satellite
Image©DigitalGlobe,
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Figure 2. Edirne Kaleiçi houses

Figure 3. Edirne Kaleiçi houses

Evaluation of the Variables Related to the Houses

House Main Plan Types

The following are the Ottoman housing plan types of Sedad Hakkı Eldem that were seen in the study area for the 70 Ottoman Houses evaluated in the Edirne Kaleiçi region utilizing the sofa-based classification system;

- Plan types with an outer sofa : 20 houses
- Plan types with an inner sofa : 45 houses
- Plan types with a central sofa : 5 houses

Figure 4. Percentages of house main plan types

Figure 5. House main plan type (GIS)

When the percentages of house main plan types are examined (Figure 4), plan type with inner sofa, with 64.29%, is predominantly encountered in Edirne Kaleiçi region. The percentage of plan type with outer sofa is 28.57% while the percentage of plan type with central sofa is found as 7.14%. The locations of all the house main plan types are indicated on the map in Figure 5.

House Sub Plan Types

The sub plan types encountered in the study area are as follows:

When the distributions of plan types with outer sofa (Table 2), based on their sub plan types, are examined;

- Outer Sofa TYPE 1 - The type of plan with an outer sofa: 7 houses
- Outer Sofa TYPE 2 - The type of plan with a supplementary sofa or with a recess in the sofa: 1 house
- Outer Sofa TYPE 6 - The type of plan with a bevelled sofa and one seating bay: 12 houses

The distributions of plan types with inner sofa (Table 2), based on their sub plan types, are;

- Inner Sofa TYPE 1 - The type of plan with two facades and an inner sofa: 1 house
- Inner Sofa TYPE 3 - The type of plan with a bevelled sofa and a supplementary sofa: 1 house
- Inner Sofa TYPE 4 - The type of plan with a staircase at the end of the sofa: 22 houses
- Inner Sofa TYPE 5 - The type of plan with a staircase in line with the rooms: 21 houses

When the distributions of plan types with central sofa (Table 2), based on their sub plan types, are evaluated;

- Central sofa TYPE 1 - The type of plan with a sofa closed in on four sides: 1 house
- Central sofa TYPE 3 - The type of plan with a sofa and two liwans⁽³⁾ (antechambers), the staircase in line with the rooms: 1 house
- Central sofa TYPE 6 - The type of plan with a sofa and an liwan (antechamber) on four sides, the staircase at the end of the sofa: 3 houses

(3) *Liwan* is a long narrow-fronted hall or vaulted portal in residential units that is often open to the outside.

Types with Outer Sofa	TYPE 1	
	TYPE 2	
	TYPE 6	
Types with Inner Sofa	TYPE 1	
	TYPE 3	
	TYPE 4	
	TYPE 5	
Types with Central Sofa	TYPE 1	
	TYPE 3	
	TYPE 6	

Table 2. House sub plan Types detected in Edirne Kaleiçi Region (Re-drawing based on Eldem, 1984, 26-27-28-29)

Figure 6. Percentages of house sub plan types

Figure 7. House sub plan type (GIS)

Inner Sofa TYPE 4 is the most common house sub plan type, accounting for 31.43% of all occurrences of plan types with inner sofas, as shown by the percentage distributions of house sub plan types (Figure 6). The second most prevalent plan type in the area is Inner Sofa TYPE 5, which is a sub type of the plan type with inner sofa (30.00%). It is followed by Outer Sofa TYPE 6, which is a sub type of the plan type with outer sofa (17.14%). In Figure 7, the locations of every form of house sub plan are depicted on a map.

Location of the House

Ten different types of houses are recognized in the study area based on where they are on the property. These include TYPE 1- On the corner part of the lot, TYPE 2- Adjacent to the short side of the lot, TYPE 3- Adjacent to the long side of the lot, TYPE 4- Adjacent to the side of the lot, TYPE 5- Occupying the whole lot, TYPE 6- On the front of the lot, TYPE 7- On the backside of the lot, TYPE 8- In the middle of lot, TYPE 9- Adjacent to the bordering lot, and TYPE 10- On the front of lot adjacent to the road.

The number of each style of house found in the area is listed below (Table 3):

- TYPE 1 - On the corner part of the lot: 33 houses
- TYPE 3 - Adjacent to the long side of the lot: 3 houses
- TYPE 4 - Adjacent to the side of the lot: 1 house
- TYPE 5 - Occupying the whole lot: 16 houses
- TYPE 6 - On the front of the lot: 10 houses
- TYPE 8 - In the middle of lot: 2 houses
- TYPE 9 - Adjacent to the bordering lot: 5 houses

Table 3. House location types detected in Edirne Kaleiçi Region (Re-drawing based on Akansel, 1990)

According to the percentage distributions of house locations (Figure 8), TYPE 1- On the Corner Part of the Lot, is the most typical house location among the examined dwellings, occurring 47.14% of the time. TYPE 5- Occupying the Whole Lot, is seen in the area in second place (22.86%), followed by TYPE 6- On the Front of the Lot, (14.29%). Figure 9 displays the locations of every type of house on the map.

Figure 8. Percentages of house locations

Figure 9. Location of house (GIS)

Areas of House

The minimum and maximum areas are determined after calculating the house areas and the mean area is then determined in accordance with those results. The average house area is 112 m², with a minimum house area of 57 m² and a maximum house area of 222 m². Equal area ranges are established in the second stage by taking into account the minimum, maximum, and mean values.

Figure 10. Percentages of house areas

Figure 11. Area of house (GIS)

The following are the area ranges and the number of houses in each range:

- S1 - (57-112 m²) : 36 houses
- S2 - (113-167 m²) : 30 houses
- S3 - (168-222 m²) : 4 houses

When house area range percentages are looked at (Figure 10), the S1 area range (57-112 m²), with 51.43%, is the most common in the area. Second, the proportion of the S2 area range (113-167 m²) is 42.86%, while the proportion of the S3 area range (168-222 m²) is 5.71%. The locations of all results are indicated on the map in Figure 11.

Entrance of House

The evaluation of the house entrances in the research region revealed three distinct categories for the entrances: entrance from the garden, entrance from the street, and entrance from the atrium. In the area, just two houses have entrances from the garden whereas 68 houses have entrances from the street.

The percentage of houses with entrances from the street is 97.14%, while the percentage of houses with entrances from the garden is 2.86%, according to the evaluation of house entrance percentages (Figure 12). The locations of the results are indicated on the map in Figure 13.

Figure 12. Percentages of house entrance types

Figure 13. Entrance of house (GIS)

Variables Related to the Lot

Lot's Geometrical Shape

Examining the geometrical shapes of the identified types of lots is performed for the 70 houses evaluated in the Edirne Kaleiçi. The lot types are categorized as follows: TYPE 1: Rectangular 1 (Ratio between 1/4- 1/2) lots, TYPE 2: Rectangular 2 (ratio equal to 1/2 or smaller) lots, TYPE 3: Square lots, TYPE 4: Polygonal lots, TYPE 5: Triangular lots, TYPE 6: L shaped lots, TYPE 7: T shaped lots, TYPE 8: U shaped lots, and TYPE 9: Amorphous lots. Table 4 lists the types found in the area, along with their numbers;

- TYPE 1 (R1 - Rectangular 1 lots) : 10 lots
- TYPE 2 (R2 - Rectangular 2 lots) : 36 lots
- TYPE 3 (S - Square lots) : 13 lots
- TYPE 4 (P - Polygonal lots) : 4 lots
- TYPE 6 (L - L shaped lots) : 7 lots

Table 4. Lot's geometrical shape detected in Edirne Kaleiçi Region (Re-drawing based on Akansel, 1990)

LOT'S GEOMETRICAL SHAPE				
TYPE 1	TYPE 2	TYPE 3	TYPE 4	TYPE 6

Figure 14. Percentages of lot's geometrical shape

Figure 15. Lot's geometrical shape (GIS)

The most common lot type, with a percentage of %51.43, is TYPE 1, as shown by the percentages of the geometrical shapes of lots in Figure 14. Second, TYPE 3 accounts for 18.57% of the population, while TYPE 2 makes for 14.29%. Figure 15 displays the placement of the geometrical shapes of the lot.

Location of Lot

According to the evaluation of the determined types in relation with the lot locations (Table 5), there exist two categories as; corner lot and row lot.

In the region, the number of corner lots is 45 while there are 25 row lots.

When the percentages are evaluated (Figure 16), corner lots are predominant in the area with the percentage of 64.29% while the percentage of row lots is 35.71%. All the locations of lots are indicated on the map in Figure 17.

Table 5. Lot location types detected in Edirne Kaleiçi Region (Re-drawing based on Akansel, 1990)

Figure 16. Percentages of lot locations

Figure 17. Location of lot (GIS)

Area of Lot

The region's lots have an average lot size of 239 m², a lowest lot area of 57 m², and a maximum lot area of 1126 m², and several values in between. Equal area ranges are developed taking these parameters into account.

The following table lists the area ranges of lots and the number of lots that fall inside each range;

- S1 - (50-239 m²) : 43 lots
- S2 - (240-418 m²) : 20 lots
- S3 - (419-595 m²) : 6 lots
- S6 - (950-1126 m²) : 1 lot

When the percentages are examined (Figure 18), S1 area range, with 61.43%, is predominantly encountered in the region. Secondly, the percentage of S2 area range is 28.57% while the percentage of S3 range is found as 8.57%. The locations of all results are indicated on the map in Figure 19.

Figure 18. Percentages of lot areas

Figure 19. Area of lot (GIS)

Plot Ratio (PAR)

The maximum and minimum values as well as the mean value are determined in this section for the lots that belong to the houses that were examined for the study. As a result, the mean PAR value is 0.60, the minimum PAR value is 0.11, and the maximum PAR value is 1.01.

Figure 20. Percentages of PAR values

Figure 21. Plot ratio (PAR) (GIS)

Equal value ranges are also defined in this document, and the quantity of lots falling inside each range is listed as;

- P1 - 0.11-0.35) : 12 lots
- P2 - (0.36-0.60) : 30 lots
- P3 - (0.61-0.85) : 8 lots
- P4 - (0.86-1.10) : 20 lots

According to the percentages of PAR values (Figure 20), P2 value range, with 42.86%, is predominantly encountered in the region. Secondly, the percentage of P4 range is 28.57% while ratio of P1 range is found as 17.14%. The locations of all results are indicated on the map in Figure 21.

Floor Area Ratio (FAR)

Minimum FAR value in the region was 0.24, maximum FAR value was 3.10, and mean FAR value is 1.26.

The FAR values and the quantity of lots lying within these ranges are determined using the equivalent value ranges, as shown below;

- F1 - (0.24-0.75) : 16 lots
- F2 - (0.76-1.26) : 26 lots
- F3 - (1.27-1.75) : 8 lots
- F4 - (1.76-2.25) : 17 lots
- F5 - (2.26-2.75) : 2 lots
- F6 - (2.75-3.10) : 1 lot

Figure 22. Percentages of FAR values

Figure 23. Floor area ratio (FAR) (GIS)

When checking the percentages of FAR value ranges (Figure 22), the F2 range, with 37.14%, is the most common in the area. Second, although the percentage of the F1 range is found to be 22.86%, the percentage of the F4 value range is 24.29%. Figure 23's map displays the locations of each outcome.

EVALUATION

In conclusion, it can be said that the plan type with an inner sofa is the most common plan type in the Edirne Kaleiçi region based on the findings of the study of house-related characteristics. This proportion is 64.29%. In terms of housing sub plan types, TYPE 4 (plan type with a staircase at the end of the sofa), is the most prevalent plan type in the area (31.43%) among sub plans of plan type with inner sofa. When the percentages of house locations are assessed, it is also discovered that the region is dominated by TYPE 1 (Corner of lot) locations, with a percentage of 47.14%. On the other hand, S1 (57-112 m²) comprises the bulk of the house area ranges (51.43%), and 97.14% of all house entrances are typically from the street. However, when the percentages of the geometrical shapes of the lot are examined, it is determined that TYPE 1 according to the evaluation of variables pertinent to the lot: Rectangular 1 (Ratio between $\frac{1}{2}$ - $\frac{1}{4}$) is the most frequently encountered lot geometry with a percentage of 51.43%. Regarding the lot location variable, corner lots are most frequently observed (64.29%) in the area. The majority of lot area ranges, is within S1 (50-239 m²) range with a percentage of 61.43%. The value range of P2 (0.36-0.60) is predominant in the region (42.86%), whereas the majority of FAR values for the lots are in the F2 (0.76-1.26) value range. These findings concerning the house and lot should be taken into account when protecting and developing the historical housing pattern. They should also be viewed as an input when developing conservation strategies. As a result, in addition to architectural inputs specific to that housing settlement, conservation plans would also incorporate urban pattern inputs pertaining to the house and lot.

CONCLUSION

The following recommendations can be made for the creation of the urban conservation plans in light of the conclusions described above regarding the role of housing and lots in the conservation and development of the urban-historical pattern of the Edirne Kaleiçi region;

- Among the plan types with inner sofa, TYPE 4 (The type of plan with a staircase at the end of the sofa) and TYPE 5 (The type of plan with a staircase in line with the rooms) were determined as the most common plan type in the traditional Ottoman houses in the region. Blueprints that use these plans as a guide and are appropriate for the new living circumstances can be created for the new houses that will be built.
- In terms of where to put the house, it could be best to put them at the corners of the lots. By doing this, it is possible to guarantee that the garden area is utilized to the fullest extent possible and to acquire two different road heights, specifically for corner lots.
- It could be preferable if the houses' entrances are on the street.
- House areas may be in the S1 (57-112 m²) area range.
- It can be ensured when preparing the subdivision plan in the empty areas in the region, that the lot geometries are TYPE 1: Rectangle 1 (Ratio between $\frac{1}{2}$ - $\frac{1}{4}$), and corner lots can be obtained by creating small block of buildings.

- The lot areas can be located in the S1 (50-239 m²) area range.
- Lot PAR values are in the P2 (0.36-0.60) range, and lot FAR values are; F2 (0.76-1.26) value range may be preferred (Saf & Ergül, 2011).

This study's aim is not to develop a decision-making process that will take the settlement of the conservation strategy. Recommended kinds, ranges, and results, including PAR, FAR, and other values, shouldn't be seen as legally binding. These findings offer a decision range that can be taken into account while creating conservation plans. It can be compared to an option-proposing design guide.

This study indicates that such a guide, which can be used from the planning stage of conservation plans, should contain the house's architectural aspects as well as the lot's urban textural features. As a result, efforts to improve the physical environment in historic city cores will have greater success.

Making generalizations from the Edirne example, which was covered in this paper, would of course not be appropriate. The Edirne field study findings can help with the creation of a zoning plan to preserve the Edirne Kaleiçi urban site. The settlement's analysis should be done for another urban site. The case of Edirne, which is examined in the context of this study, can be used as an example in the investigation of other urban areas. On the other hand, the outcomes of the analysis carried out in various locations can help us identify the variations and parallels among the settlements.

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Edirne Kaleiçi Bölgesinde Tarihi Kentsel Dokuda Konut-Parsel Özelliklerinin Analizi ⁽¹⁾

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Özet

(1) Bu çalışma Hayriye Oya Saf tarafından 2011 yılında tamamlanan "A Method for the Analysis of Lot-House Relations in Ottoman Housing Pattern" isimli Doktora tezinden (Saf, 2011) üretilmiştir.

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Morfolojik analiz metoduna dayanan bu çalışma; tarihsel kentlerde konut dokusunun, konut ve parsel ilişkisi parametreleri üzerinden çözümlenmesi gerekliliğini savlamaktadır. Analiz sonuçlarının görselleştirilmesinde Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemi (CBS) programı kullanılmıştır. Ayrıca, böyle bir çözümleme sonucunda elde edilecek yeni veriler ile kentsel sit alanlarında koruma amaçlı imar planlarının hazırlanmasına yardımcı olacak bir veri tabanı oluşturmayı hedeflemektedir. Kısaca, korunacak yapının nasıl bir parselde oturduğu, bu parsel içinde nasıl konumlandığı ve bunun genel eğilime uyumlu ya da aykırı olup olmadığı, koruma amaçlı imar planını hazırlayan ekipler için girdi oluşturacaktır. Bu çalışma ile elde edilen sonuçların, tarihsel konut dokusunun korunmasında ve geliştirilmesinde bir tasarım rehberi olarak kullanılması beklenmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Edirne-Kaleiçi, Osmanlı Konut Dokusu, Koruma Amaçlı İmar Planı, Kentsel Sit Alanı, Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemi (CBS)